

Paper 26**ACCOUNTING STANDARDS AND FINANCIAL STATEMENTS OF MANGALORE CHEMICALS AND FERTILIZERS LTD AND KARNATAKA BANK LTD****Ms Sandhya Rani*, Caroleena Janefer****

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Abstract:

A company consists of varied number of users who contribute for the growth and prosperity of the organization. It is the duty in the part of the company to be accountable to such users. This can be achieved by summarizing the working of the organization in terms of monetary value in its financial statements. It is required to maintain these financial statements in a way which is acceptable and understandable to all the users of financial statements. This paper is based on the implication of accounting standards on the company's two different sectors, Mangalore Chemicals and Fertilizers Ltd and Karnataka Bank Ltd.

Keywords: Accounting Standards, Financial Statements.**1. INTRODUCTION**

A company consists of varied number of users who contribute for the growth and prosperity of the organization. It is the duty in the part of the company to be accountable to such users. This can be achieved by summarizing the working of the organization in terms of monetary value in its financial statements. It is required to maintain these financial statements in a way which is acceptable and understandable to all the users of financial statements.

2. CONCEPT OF ACCOUNTING STANDARDS

Accounting Standards (ASs) are written policy documents issued by expert accounting body or by government or other regulatory body covering the aspects of recognition, measurement, presentation and disclosure of accounting transactions in the financial statements. The ostensible purpose of the standard setting bodies is to promote the dissemination of timely and useful financial information to investors and certain other parties having interest in the company's economic performance. Accounting Standards reduces the accounting alternatives in the preparation of the financial statements within the bounds of rationality, thereby ensuring comparability of financial statements of different enterprise.

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To analyze the disclosures specified of the Accounting Standards adopted.
2. To find out the changes in the applicability Accounting Standards in past 5 years.

3. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Accounting standard has known is a varied concept consisting of 27 different standards applicable for different incomes and expenses. This study is based on the implication of such accounting standards on the company's two different sectors. The jurisdiction of study is in the city of Mangalore. The first is the study on 'Mangalore Chemicals and Fertilizers Ltd, Mangalore' which is manufacturing company on fertilizers. The second is on 'Karnataka Bank Ltd' a banking company

1. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY OF STUDY

1. Primary data: Financial statements obtained from the annual report of the company
2. Secondary data: Files, books, journals and periodicals, manuals and text book. Which have already been passed through the statistical process are the secondary data used.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

The **Author Bhattacharyya** in his **book Indian Accounting Standard** explains about different accounting standards, conceptual framework and presentation of balance sheet and also the profit and loss account. In the first chapter, the author mentions about the Accounting Standards Board (ASB) which was issued by ICAI in the year 2000. Further the author speaks about the purpose of framework issues by ASB, the concept of financial reporting and financial statements. For the preparation of the financial statements there is mainly three assumptions- accrual concept, going concern, consistency. In the second chapter, it states that the presentation of the financial statements, stipulates that a complete set of financial statements consists of balance sheet, income statement, a statement showing changes in equity, cash flow statement and accounting policies and explanatory notes.

The authors **Bruce Bennett, Michael Bradbury and Helen Prangnell** in their journal (Volume 42) place a distinction between rules based and principles based standards is not well defined and is subject to a variety of interpretations. Yet there is a commonly held view that the FASB's standards are rules based and the IASB's standards are principles based. This article identifies the basis of this distinction. For research and development, the article compares the FASB standard with two principles based standards. For each standard we identify and classify rules and judgments, and observe the level of justifications for the rules and assistance to support the judgments. The three standards have rules, are based on principles, and require the exercise of professional judgment; the less conservative standard requires more judgments and, unexpectedly, more rules. The results suggest that the rules based versus principles based distinction are not meaningful, except in relative terms. They conclude that a relatively more principles based standards regime requires professional judgment at both the transaction level (substance over form) and at the financial statement level ('true and fair view' override). Furthermore, it is suggested that any FASB and IASB convergence will require agreement on the weightings given to the qualitative characteristics.

3. FINDINGS

In case of Mangalore Chemicals and Fertilizers Ltd-

1. AS1: The similar accounting policies followed by the company for five financial years are use of estimates, borrowing costs, valuation of inventories, foreign currency transactions, revenue recognition, depreciation, leases, earnings per share, intangible assets retirement benefits, taxes, intangible assets, non-financial assets, segment reporting etc.

2. AS2: Inventories are valued lower of cost and net realizable value for all the five financial years. The disclosure of inventory values in detail helps the users of the financial statements in ratio analysis in the financial statements.

3. AS3: Mangalore chemical and fertilizers Ltd follow 'indirect method' of preparation of cash flow statement for all the five years. It divides the statement into three parts that is cash flow from operating activities, cash flow from investing activities, cash flow from financial activities.

4. AS9: The company follows the same principal of revenue recognition for all the five years. Revenue in case of manufacturing company is in form of sale of goods, interest, grants or subsidies received and such other form.

5. AS10: In the statements of the company fixed assets are capitalized at cost, inclusive of financial charges on borrowed funds related to acquisition of fixed assets, depreciation (then AS-6) on fixed assets is calculated on straight line method as per the rates prescribed under Schedule XIV of the Companies Act, 1956. Written down value of insurance spares is charged off in the year of replacement of the existing part in the fixed asset.

6. AS13: The schedules of the company state that the in long term investments are valued at cost. Provision on diminution of long-term investments is deducted from such value of investments.

7. AS15: The benefits given by the company for its employees includes provident fund, gratuity, superannuation fund, pension scheme, leave encashment benefits for the five financial years.

8. AS18: The company has many related parties in their organization which includes associates, holding company, key managerial personnel.

9. AS19: The bank calculates its basic and diluted earnings per share. The EPS has decreased over the years up to the financial year 2016-17 and has increased for the financial year 2017-18.

In case of Karnataka Bank Ltd-

1. AS1: The similar accounting policies followed by the bank for five financial years are revenue recognition, investments, derivative contracts, advances, fixed assets, depreciation, foreign currency transactions, employee stock options, employee benefits, segment reporting, share issue expenses, earning per share, taxes, provisions and net profit.

2. AS2: This accounting standard is not applicable for a banking company as it is not in the line of business of production and manufacturing of goods.

Hence Karnataka Bank Ltd has no inventories in the balance sheet as they are into borrowing and lending of funds.

3. AS3: Karnataka Bank follows indirect method of preparation of cash flow statement. It divides the statement into three parts that is cash flow from operating activities, cash flow from investing activities, cash flow from financial activities.

4. AS9: The main sources of revenue are: interest on loans, interest on investments, fees income, FOREX operations etc. Income is accounted for on an accrual basis except in respect of income from non-performing assets, commission, exchange, Funded Interest Term Loan (FITL) and rent on safe deposit lockers, which are all accounted on cash basis.

5. AS10: The main two assets in the bank are premises and other fixed assets which includes furniture and fixtures. Land and building are capitalized based on conveyance or letter of allotment or physical position of the property. Software is capitalized along with computer hardware and included under Other Fixed Assets. Depreciation is charged on the basis of Written down Value as per schedule XIV. Premium paid on lease hold properties are charged off over the lease period.

6. AS13: Investments are classified under the heads 'Head to Maturity', 'Available for Sale' and 'Held for Trading' categories and valued under RBI guidelines. The value, net depreciation is shown in Balance Sheet. The investments of a banking company may be categorized into two: one investment made within India and other investments made outside India.

7. AS15: The statement states that the contribution made by the bank to Provident Fund and Contributory pension scheme is charged to profit and loss account. Contribution to the recognized Gratuity Fund, Pension fund and en-cashable leave are determined and recognized in the accounts based on actuarial valuation at Balance Sheet. Provision for short term employee benefits are accounted for on estimated basis.

8. AS18: There are no related parties as such in case of banking companies except that it contains of key management personnel. The company has no holding or a subsidiary company with whom it has trading relations.

9. AS20: The bank calculates its basic and diluted earnings per share. The EPS is increased for the year 2014-15 and gradually decreased for the next three years.

10. SUGGESTIONS

1. The company needs to mention in detail the accounting standards adopted and if not the reasons for it.

2. The form of disclosure of one year should be the same in the upcoming years.

3. It is observed that the closing balance of previous year do not be the same opening balance in the next year. The changes in such amount should be disclosed.

4. The presentation of notes to accounts differs from year to year leading in difficulty in analysis.

5. The company should note that the disclosure procedure used should be understood easily by a layman who does not have accounting knowledge.

6. It is seen in the project; the data of previous year differs when it is consolidated and written with the figures of the next year. The company should disclose the reasons for such changes.

11. CONCLUSION

After this study it can be conclude that-The accounting standards adopted are different in manufacturing sector and different in banking sector.It is compulsory for the company to follow the rules of the accounting standards given by ICAI as it helps in better presentation, analysis and comparison of data.Any change in accounting standards should be implemented by the company in its books of accounts within the time frame given by the board.Knowledge of Accounting Standard in the company helps in better presentation of the financial data.

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